

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Malonic Acid and its Dimethyl Ester by Cerium(IV) Sulphate

V. K. VAIDYA*, S. N. JOSHI and G. V. BAKORE

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001

Manuscript received 4 May 1987, revised 28 December 1987, accepted 29 February 1988

Kinetics of the oxidation of malonic acid and dimethyl ester of malonic acid by cerium(IV) sulphate in sulphuric acid medium show first order dependence each in substrate and cerium(IV). The reactive oxidant species are $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$. The oxidation of acid is found to be faster as compared to its ester. A tentative mechanism has been proposed.

KINETICS of oxidation of malonic acid and its diethyl ester by Ce^{IV} have been studied by several workers¹⁻⁷, however, two different mechanisms have been proposed for this reaction. The first mechanism involves a rapid formation of Ce^{IV} complex (activated) followed by its slow decomposition and in the second mechanism, the oxidation proceeds without complex formation. In view of these divergent views it was considered of interest to undertake the title investigation to have a clear understanding of the mechanism of this oxidation reaction.

Experimental

Ceric sulphate (E.M.), malonic acid (Riedel A.R), dimethyl ester of malonic acid (Koch-Light), sodium bisulphate (B.D.H.) and sodium perchlorate (Riedel) were used. Perchloric acid (70%, AnalaR) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. All other chemicals were of Sarabhai-Merck grade. Ceric sulphate solutions were prepared by dissolving it in 1M H_2SO_4 . Double-distilled water was used to prepare all solutions. The reaction was conducted in dark-coloured bottles. All the experiments were carried out in acetic acid (25%, v/v) in presence of H_2SO_4 .

The requisite amount of a reacting solutions was separately equititrated at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.02^\circ$). Ceric sulphate of known concentration was pre-equititrated at the desired temperature and was rapidly added to the substrate (however, in case of the ester, it was added last). Aliquots were drawn at regular intervals and quenched in a known excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate. The excess ferrous ions was then back-titrated against standard Ce^{IV} solution with ferroin as indicator.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometric investigation reveals that 1 mol of malonic acid requires 8 mol of Ce^{IV} whereas the

corresponding dimethyl ester requires 16 mol of Ce^{IV} . The final products of oxidation were characterised as formaldehyde and formic acid⁸⁻¹⁰. The reaction mixture also gave positive spot-test for glyoxalic acid¹¹ while CO_2 was confirmed by lime-water test. The induced reduction of mercuric chloride by the reaction mixture indicated participation of free radicals¹². When the concentrations of malonic acid and perchloric acid were in excess, the disappearance of ceric sulphate followed a first order rate law.

Varying initial $[Ce^{IV}]$ did not effect the rate constant, confirming the order in Ce^{IV} as one. The plot of $\log k$ vs $\log$ [Substrate] was linear with a unit slope, indicating the order in substrate also as one. There was no kinetic evidence for intermediate complex formation between the substrate and oxidants. However, absorbances of two solutions (blank and reaction mixture) did change. This indicated that either the concentration of reversible complex is small or sulphate-cerate complex of the ester of malonic acid decomposed rapidly. Further, the oxidation of malonic acid is faster than dimethyl ester of malonic acid.

From the kinetic point of view, the real problem in oxidation by Ce^{IV} is the multiplicity of cerium species, probably each one with its own characteristic rate constant. Using the values the equilibrium constants k_1 , k_2 and k_3 for the formation of various ceric sulphate complexes¹³ and the experimental data (dependence of reaction rate on H^+ ions; Tables 1 and 2) concentration of various Ce^{IV} sulphate species¹⁴ have been calculated (Table 3). The dependence of rate on bisulphate (Table 4) rules out the possibility of Ce^{4+} and $Ce(SO_4)^{2+}$ as the reactive species. The only species left in the present case are $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and $Ce(SO_4)_3^{2-}$. Assuming both of them to be reactive in this oxidation, a mechanism consistent with the kinetic data has been proposed (Scheme). This mechanism

*Department of Chemistry, M. L. V. Government College, Bhilwara-311 001.

confirms the mechanism proposed by the earlier workers^{1,5}.

where, R=H or CH₃; Ce⁴⁺=Ce(SO₄)₂ and Ce(SO₄)₃²⁻.

Scheme

The rate law, in accord with Scheme is given by equation (1),

$$\frac{k_1}{\text{Substrate}} = \frac{k' \text{H}^+}{k_2 \text{HSO}_4^-} + k'' \quad (1)$$

where, k' and k'' are the rate constants for the oxidation of substrate (malonic acid and its dimethyl ester) by Ce(SO₄)₂ and Ce(SO₄)₃²⁻, respectively. At constant H⁺, equation (1) reduces to

$$\frac{k_1}{\text{Substrate}} = \frac{a}{\text{HSO}_4^-} + b \quad (2)$$

where, $a = k' \text{H}^+ / k_2$ and $b = k''$. The value of k' have been evaluated from the values of a and b determined by least-square method from the data (Table 4) and their values are given in Table 5.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF H⁺ ION ON REACTION RATE

Substrate = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, Ce^{IV} = 4.0 × 10⁻³ M, Temp. = 308 K, Solvent, glacial acetic acid : water = 1 : 3 (v/v), μ = 1.5 M

H ₂ SO ₄	NaHSO ₄	Malonic acid k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	Dimethyl ester of malonic acid k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
1.25	0.25	57.57	4.72
1.00	0.50	44.18	8.52
0.75	0.75	35.81	2.58
0.50	1.0	25.06	2.06
0.25	1.25	18.80	1.15

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF H⁺ ION ON REACTION RATE

Substrate = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, Ce^{IV} = 4.0 × 10⁻³ M, Temp. = 308 K, Solvent, glacial acetic acid : water = 1 : 3 (v/v), μ = 1.5 M, H₂SO₄ = 0.1 M

HClO ₄ M	NaClO ₄ M	Malonic acid k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	Dimethyl ester of malonic acid k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.15	1.25	4.60	2.21
0.40	1.0	9.21	4.11
0.65	0.75	18.81	5.95
0.90	0.50	17.27	8.97
1.15	0.25	22.65	10.36

TABLE 3—CONCENTRATION FOR Ce^{IV} SPECIES

H⁺ = 0.5 M

Species	HSO ₄ ⁻ = 1.0 M	HSO ₄ ⁻ = 0.25 M
Ce ⁴⁺	8.71 × 10 ⁻⁹	5.19 × 10 ⁻⁷
Ce(SO ₄) ₂ ²⁺	6.10 × 10 ⁻⁹	9.08 × 10 ⁻⁴
Ce(SO ₄) ₂	2.48 × 10 ⁻⁶	9.08 × 10 ⁻³
Ce(SO ₄) ₃ ²⁻	0.97	0.91

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF BISULPHATE ION ON REACTION RATE

Substrate = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, Ce^{IV} = 4.0 × 10⁻³ M, Temp. = 308 K, Solvent, glacial acetic acid : water = 1 : 3 (v/v), μ = 1.5 M, H⁺ = 0.5 M

NaHSO ₄ M	NaClO ₄ M	Malonic acid k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	Dimethyl ester of malonic acid k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.25	0.75	76.76	3.84
0.50	0.50	60.64	3.40
0.75	0.25	49.89	2.92
1.00	—	44.52	2.55

TABLE 5—RATE CONSTANT FOR Ce^{IV} SPECIES

HSO₄⁻ = 0.25 and 1.0 M, H⁺ = 0.5 M, Temp. = 308 K

	Malonic acid	Dimethyl ester of malonic acid
a	10.41 × 10 ⁻³	0.39 × 10 ⁻³
k' (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	4.16	0.156
b	36.27 × 10 ⁻³	2.36 × 10 ⁻³
k'' (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	36.27 × 10 ²	2.36 × 10 ⁻¹

The reaction was studied at different temperatures to evaluate the activation parameters. The values of energy of activation for the oxidation of malonic acid and its dimethyl ester were evaluated as 53.9 and 63.5 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively.

The rate of oxidation of dimethyl ester is slower than that of malonic acid in H₂SO₄ medium. The slow rate of oxidation may be explained firstly by the less electron-withdrawing inductive effect (-I) of COOCH₃ than COOH group, and secondly there is a possibility of steric effect of CH₃ group which hinders the formation of Ce^{IV}-ester complex, i.e. reduces the concentration of the complex and hence slows down the rate of the oxidation of the ester.

References

1. R. L. YADAV and W. V. BHAGWAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **41**, 389.
2. K. K. SENGUPTA and S. ADITYA, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Frankfurt)*, 1963, **38**, 25.
3. R. K. PRASAD and S. N. TRIPATHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 358.
4. M. IGNACZAK, *Soc. Sci. Lodz. Acta Chim.*, 1972, **17**, 135.
5. F. TISCHLER and J. I. MORROW, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 2286.
6. V. K. VAIDYA, S. N. JOSHI and G. V. BAKORE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 865.
7. V. K. VAIDYA, S. N. JOSHI and G. V. BAKORE, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1987, **268**, 364.
8. N. D. CHERONIS and T. S. MAO, "Organic Functional Group Analysis by Micro- and Semi-micro Methods", Interscience, New York, 1964, p. 504.
9. T. K. EINERT and E. SCREFFEL, *Analyst*, 1949, **74**, 610.
10. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, New York, 1966, 453.
11. Ref. 10, p. 483.
12. A. Y. DRUMMONDS and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2836.
13. T. J. HARDWICK and E. ROBERTSON, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1951, **29**, 818.
14. R. DAYAL and G. V. BAKORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 1083.
15. A. Y. DRUMMONDS and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2456; Z. AMJAD and MCAULEY, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 304.